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MODERN APPROACHES TO LANGUAGE TEACHING IN UZBEKISTAN

Annotation : This article is about modern approaches to language teaching in Uzbekistan. Modern approach of ELT is one of the effective teaching method. If language teachers use this way of teaching method it will a great number of opportunities to learners improve their communicative skill.

Key words: *Approach, teaching, language, fluency, accuracy, self-confidence, communicative classroom, method, knowledge*

Modern approach of English language teaching is usually characterized as a broad approach to teaching, rather than as a teaching method with a clearly defined set of classroom practices. English language teaching places great emphasis on helping pupils use the target language in a variety of contexts and on learning language functions. Its primary focus is on helping learners create meaning rather than helping them develop perfectly grammatical structures or acquire native-like pronunciation. This means that successfully learning a foreign language is assessed in terms of how well learners have developed their communicative competence, which can loosely be defined as their ability to apply knowledge of a language with adequate proficiency to communicate.

Historically, modern approaches of ELT are divided into 3 phases: traditional approaches; classic communicative language teaching; current communicative language teaching. These phases are differ from each other according to what kind of method they focus on that time. For instance, in the first phase, grammar is considered very important issue in Communicative approach. Year by year as learning process

changes, teaching methods also develops and teachers look for techniques to implement the best method.

The Direct Method

The Direct Method is also known as the Oral or Natural method. It's based on the active involvement of the student in both speaking and listening to the new language in realistic everyday situations. The process consists of a gradual acquisition of grammatical structure and vocabulary. The learner is encouraged to think in the target language rather than translate. He or she hears and uses the language before seeing it written.

The Grammar-Translation Method

This method grew from the traditional method of teaching Latin and Greek. The method is based on analysis of the written language using translation exercises, reading comprehension and written imitation of texts. Learning mainly involves the mastery of grammatical rules and memorization of vocabulary lists.

The Audio-Lingual Method

This self-teaching method is also known as the Aural-Oral method. The learning is based on repetition of dialogues and phrases about every day situations. These phrases are imitated, repeated, and drilled to make the response automatic. Reading and writing are both reinforcements of what the learner practices.

Every method has controversial sides. English language teaching also has advantages and slight disadvantages. In a nutshell, the preferences of this communicative approach are interesting, useful, authentic, harmonious... and it helps to encourage pupils and increase their confidence themselves. The downsides are having difficulties to make flawless evaluation, limited instructional hours, not suitable for all

levels, losing control. After using several times the activities of ELT, teachers can manage to decrease the disadvantages. Also fluency and accuracy have a great role to develop Communicative language teaching. It is impossible to imagine communicative approach without them.

To sum up, modern approach of ELT is one of the effective teaching method. If language teachers use this way of teaching method it will a great number of opportunities to learners improve their communicative skill. Initially, it will be difficult both teacher and pupils to adapt this method, but it makes a good resolution on pupils` self-confidence during speaking. Due to using fluency and accuracy activities at the same time in communicative classroom support pupils to become a well-qualified, fluent speaker.

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